

1 **Changes in recombination activating gene *RAG1* expression result in Xist activation or repression.**

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6 We describe here induction of Xist following induction of a double strand break in the DNA (sensed by
7 DNA-PKc) produced by a gene with immune-restricted function, the recombination activating nuclease
8 *RAG1*, demonstrating that a double stranded break in the genome can cause activation or silencing of
9 Xist, whether associated with genomic instability (unintentional damage) or an intentional result of gene
10 rearrangement events and caused by an enzyme with the ability to induce a double strand break.
11 Importantly, we provide evidence that suggests Xist imprinting-based control of the genes of the Igf locus
12 and growth hormone (GH) family genes and a growth phenotype associated with RAG1 loss or mutation
13 are biologically related events involving growth factor signaling in the context of damage of or a break in
14 the genomic DNA.
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